

Educational Institution Leaders Development Model of Legal Literacy Development

Feruz Makhmatkosimovna Kuchkarova¹, Zafar Mahmudovich Ziyavitdinov²

¹ PhD, Professor of the Department of Education, Kokand University, Uzbekistan

² Master's student in the field of management of educational institutions, Kokand University, Uzbekistan

Abstract:

In this article, the complex of legal literacy, legal education, legal education, legal literacy is highlighted.

Keywords: legal literacy, legal education, legal education, legal literacy improvement complex.

Legal literacy is part of a society's culture. It mediates in all the main areas of the legal life of society: legislation, law-making, rights and freedoms of citizens, the state mechanism, the principles and methods of its activity, legal consciousness in all its types and levels, and, therefore, it is an important criterion of the quality of the legal life of society. , it can be expressed by the concept of legal culture. It is the degree and level of progressive legal achievements embodied in human activity and its results. Legal literacy defines the criterion of legal civilization of the state and society, their legal development. It is an indicator of the high level of legal consciousness of society, and it describes the most important cultural and legal values that serve as "specific" to the family of civilized people of the world.

Legal education should be continuous and should be given from youth. Children should be aware of the rules of behavior in pre-school educational institutions, get basic understanding of moral and some legal norms, expand and deepen this knowledge in the future during education, acquire a clearly expressed legal character. necessary. Ensuring free access to legal information for everyone, creating realistic conditions for everyone to improve their legal knowledge allows citizens to properly exercise their rights and freedoms, fulfill their duties, and consciously and actively participate in the political life of society.

It is necessary to eliminate the one-sided orientation of legal education and education, left over from the past, to provide information - enlightenment, and connect it more closely with the tasks of strengthening legality, protecting the rights and freedoms of citizens. It is necessary to keep in mind that legal education is not limited to educating people in the spirit of law and legality, legal enlightenment, forming a positive attitude towards the law and the law, but also finds its fulfillment in the socio-legal activity of a person, his legal culture. . The improvement of the legal education and training of the population is achieved by creating the mechanisms of education and training that have not yet been used, using them effectively, introducing new forms and means of education and training, and strengthening the material and technical basis.

The main measures to strengthen legal education and training are as follows:

- the state, as the main organizer of legal education and training, regularly improves the methods and tools of education and training, and the structure of institutions directly engaged in this activity;
- helps to form alternative systems of legal education and legal education;
- to ensure broad cooperation of state structures and public associations in improving the legal culture of the population;
- coordination of this activity, identification of tasks that cannot be postponed and in the future

In September 2015, 192 UN member states of the world accepted the "Change of our world: Agenda for sustainable development until 2030" program and its monitoring obligations.[1]

In 2016, the UN offered our country the approach "Comprehensive implementation, acceleration and support of development policy measures to achieve the goals of sustainable development" (MAPS). In this approach, three acceleration areas (accelerators) are covered for broad reforms. The first of these areas is "Improving the effectiveness and accountability of governance systems" and it specifically recognizes that "Effective governance is a cross-cutting and key catalyst for achieving all other sustainable development goals".[2]

This situation indicates that there is a need to constantly conduct research on the improvement of the management system, the selection, training and qualification of managerial (young) personnel, the creation of conditions related to the higher level of their knowledge and their scientific improvement. gives.[3]

In the "Strategy of actions on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021", it is a priority to introduce effective forms and methods of personnel selection, centralized selection of personnel in the public service, and the introduction of the "person identification" system that meets modern requirements. was designated as one of the directions.[4]

The problem of learning the personality of the leader has been an important issue in all periods of human society. The main reason for this is that, firstly, the social relations of each period required someone to be at a high level in terms of social status, and secondly, the way of life, prosperity, level, well-being, and happy marriage of people depended on the person of this high position, his it depends on different qualities and characteristics.[5]

One of the most important advantages of a leader is that he knows the external environment, adapts to it in different situations, and can cultivate stable behavioral norms. Because the leader should know and appreciate the socio-economic achievements of the organization and be able to feel them mentally.

Legal literacy of the heads of educational institutions is important for the effectiveness and legitimacy of the educational process. This model provides a comprehensive approach to legal literacy.

I. Basic Elements of the Model

1. Diagnosis and assessment
2. Educational programs and training
3. Development of practical skills
4. Legal advice and sources of information
5. Monitoring and evaluation

II. Diagnosis and Evaluation

- Initial assessment: diagnostic tests to determine the existing legal knowledge of managers.
- Determination of individual requirements: Creating a plan of individual legal knowledge and skills for each manager.

III. Educational programs and training

- Basic Legal Courses: Courses in basic legal areas such as constitutional law, education law, labor law, finance and tax law.
- Special trainings: practical trainings on management of the institution, solving legal issues.
- Online courses and webinars: Distance learning options.

IV. Development of practical skills

- Case Study and Analysis: Developing practical skills by analyzing concrete legal situations.
- Simulation and role-playing games: Improving the legal decision-making skills of managers by simulating legal situations.
- Legal internships: practical training and internships.

V. Legal Advice and Information Resources

- Legal Consultations: A group of consultants to provide ongoing legal assistance.
- Information Resources: Regular information about legal news, legislative changes and regulatory documents.
- Electronic Libraries and Portal: Legal resources, educational materials and database.

VI. Monitoring and Evaluation

- Regular Evaluation: Evaluation and monitoring of the results of training programs.
- Feedback and Suggestions: An opportunity for leaders to express their thoughts and suggestions.
- Analysis of results: Analysis of the general results of the development of legal literacy and preparation of a report.

VII. Practical application of the model

1. Initial stage
 - Diagnostics: An initial assessment and diagnostics is conducted for each leader.
 - Individual plans: An educational plan based on individual requirements and needs is drawn up.

2. Educational process

- Educational courses and trainings: trainings are conducted based on the established educational programs.
- Practical training: practical skills are developed through case studies, simulations and practicums.

3. Monitoring and evaluation

- Intermediate evaluation: The knowledge and skills acquired at each stage are evaluated.
- Final assessment: Overall results and level of development are evaluated.

VIII. Expected Results

- The legal knowledge and practical skills of the heads of educational institutions will increase.
- Management of the institution on a legal basis will be improved.
- Increases efficiency in compliance with legislation and solving legal problems.
- Improving the quality of general education and the efficiency of the institution.

In conclusion, it can be said that this model offers a complex and systematic approach to the development of legal literacy of the heads of educational institutions. The successful implementation of the model serves to increase the efficiency of the educational institution.

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